

FEATURES OF USING MODERN METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEED-STRENGTH QUALITIES OF QUALIFIED CYCLISTS

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The fact that in recent years, Uzbek sports, with its high results, have glorified our country before the world community, thousands of sports complexes meeting international standards are being built, and the most prestigious competitions are being held in various regions of our country, is a practical result of this work. As an example, we can cite the achievements of our athletes at the XXXI Summer Olympic and XV Paralympic Games held in 2016 in the Brazilian city of Rio de Janeiro. Physical education and sports should serve not only to train talented athletes, but also to ensure a healthy gene pool and raise a harmoniously developed generation. It is known that the development of children's sports is determined not only by the material and technical aspects of the issue, but also by the importance of attracting the younger generation to physical culture and sports on a global scale, organizing classes on a scientific basis, and effectively forming physical fitness, which is the fundamental basis of sportsmanship. In addition, the health-improving and educational functions of physical education are divided into the following: you will be in a good mood throughout the day; your work will be productive, your creative activity will be strong, the nervous system will be balanced, you will be calm and thoughtful; feelings of activity, initiative, courage, friendship will be formed; regular physical exercises lead to the formation of hygienic skills, the amount of fat in the body will decrease, you will become compact, agile, and agile; your muscles will tighten, your figure will be beautiful and graceful; blood flow in the vessels will improve, the flow of oxygen and nutrients to the body and organs will improve.

According to researchers' views, the effectiveness of using a complex of speed-strength exercises in the practical training of cyclists has been confirmed. Such physical education in kindergartens ensures children's preparation for the new school daily routine, and also creates certain opportunities for better adaptation to school. It was found that the selected complex of exercises for children - including running, ball exercises, and rope activities - yielded positive results. The subjects successfully mastered these exercises and performed them with enthusiasm.

Regular exercise with kindergarten pupils during walks leads to an improvement in physical fitness, mobility, and, most importantly, health of children, which confirms the expediency of using a complex of speed-strength exercises in the practical training of cyclists.

Such physical education in kindergartens ensures the preparation of children for the new school schedule, and also creates a certain opportunity for further adaptation to school. It was established that the selected complex of running exercises, ball exercises, rope exercises for children had a positive effect, the subjects successfully mastered and performed such exercises with enthusiasm. Regular exercise during walks with kindergarten pupils leads to an improvement in physical fitness, mobility, and, most importantly, health of children, and is aimed at improving physical fitness.

After scientific work, the results of the 30 m run, standing long jump, and high jump improved within 10 months. Particularly positive results were noted in the experimental group in jumping and throwing exercises (changes were observed in jumping by 13-15 cm, in throwing by 1 m). In addition, during the training, exercises with a ball, rope, and walking were used to strengthen the foot and prevent flat feet.

In conclusion, it can be said that less attention is paid by teachers and coaches to cross-country running in physical education classes and classes for schoolchildren, and the organization and conduct of cycling competitions among schoolchildren has also decreased. Therefore, cycling has shown its effectiveness in improving the physical fitness, physical and functional development, and the development of endurance qualities of general secondary school students, and it has been proven in practice that when regularly organizing and conducting cross-country runs in physical education classes and among schoolchildren, it increases the physical fitness and endurance of schoolchildren.

Conclusion, it can be said that less attention is paid by teachers and coaches to cross-country running in physical education classes and classes for schoolchildren, and the organization and conduct of cycling competitions among schoolchildren has also decreased. Therefore, cycling has proven its effectiveness in improving physical fitness, physical and functional development, and developing endurance qualities in general secondary school students, and it has been proven in practice that regularly organizing and conducting cross-country runs in physical education classes and among schoolchildren increases their physical fitness and endurance.

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